

ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic created huge amounts of information about confirmed cases, deaths, testing, and vaccination worldwide and required the effective data processing and analysis system. The proposed project is a detailed data-oriented model to merge, process and visualize big data of COVID-19 to derive useful data. The suggested system suggests some of the major issues of the current methods, including the absence of standardisation, inconsistency of data sources, and fragmentation.

The methodology consists in gathering various heterogeneous data and turn them into a single form using data cleaning, preprocessing and standardization procedures. The analysis of key epidemiological data, including the Case Fatality Rate (CFR) and the Test Positivity Rate, adds further insight to this system. Additionally, various visualization techniques, such as choropleth maps, bar charts, scatter plots and histograms, are used to represent complex data in a readily interpretable and understandable manner.

The findings reflect the trends in the world, such as the unequal distribution of cases, differences in vaccination coverage, and testing and confirmed cases association. The suggested architecture proves to be more scalable, automated, and integrative, as opposed to current systems, which is why it is applicable in large-scale analysis and decision support. The system is also flexible to real-time data integration, and can be further expanded with predictive analytics to be used in the future in monitoring the health.

On balance, the current project is efficient and viable to solve the problem of learning the dynamics of a pandemic and facilitate data-driven decision-making among researchers and analysts, as well as policymakers.

Keywords: COVID-19, Data Visualization, Data Integration, Pandas, Plotly, Case Fatality Rate (CFR), Test Positivity Rate, Healthcare Analytics.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of covid-19 pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic is one of the biggest public health crises of our time due to the new coronavirus, SARS - CoV-2, initially detected in December 2019. The pandemic spread faster than ever in the world and infected millions of people, causing a disturbance in healthcare, economies and lives in a mass scale. The pandemic posed enormous challenges to governments and health authorities on the continents to monitor the virus and control its spread. The COVID-19 pandemic brought the vital role of data analysis to light in dealing with health crises. Vast quantities of health data - including numbers of confirmed cases, deaths, positivity rates and vaccine distributions - accumulated daily, requiring robust analysis and presentation to effectively track the spread and guide decision - making.

1.2. Origin and epicenter of the virus

Wuhan was the first epicenter of the COVID-19 outbreak as it is where the virus was first reported. Initial outbreaks were associated with a seafood and live animal market which indicated zoonotic. International travel was the cause of the rapid spread of the virus in China and later in other countries.

Figure 1: The source of COVID-19 in Wuhan, China

After a couple of months, the virus went outside Asia and hit Europe, North America and other continents. With the high mobility of people and globalization, the spread of the virus became fast, and a local outbreak was transformed into a global one.

1.3. Transmission and spread of covid-19

The COVID-19 spreads mostly by means of respiratory droplets produced by an infected individual when coughing, sneezing, or speaking. It may also be transmitted through airborne infections in confined areas and contact with surfaces that are contaminated. Human-to-human infections contributed significantly to the high rate of the virus spreading.

Figure 2: COVID-19 (Droplet, Airborne, Surface) Modes of Transmission

Population density, travel trends, and absence of early containment measures are some of the factors that led to the massive spread. The nature of modern societies, which were interconnected, enabled the virus to travel fast across borders.

1.4. Pattern of spread to the rest of the world (epicenter to global)

The virus was transmitted at various stages after appearing in Wuhan. First, the neighbouring Asian countries were impacted before Europe, which became a hot-spot in early 2020. Later on, the whole of North America and other continents had major outbreaks. International travels, trade relations and the high mobile populations among nations were the key factors that spearheaded the rapid internationalization of the disease.

The distribution trend indicated that those countries that have high international travel and population density in cities were more affected seriously. Great urban centers were the centers of transmission and increased the pace of the infection. In most areas, the slow adoption of prevention strategies including lockdowns and restrictions on traveling also added to the fast rate of the cases. The sudden increase in infections overwhelmed healthcare systems in various countries, particularly at the beginning of the waves. The spread of the virus through variants also contributed to the rapid spread of the virus and the formation of waves of infection in various regions. During

Figure 3: World Map of COVID-19 (Epicenter to World)

the course of time, the virus has spread even to the relatively distant and less interconnected locations, becoming a truly worldwide pandemic.

The large scale of the pandemic demonstrated the need to detect and respond to the pandemic early, in a coordinated manner, and a system that tracks the data to make future outbreaks manageable.

1.5. Population (continent-wise analysis) impact of covid-19

The effects of COVID-19 were different in various continents because of the population density, healthcare system, government efforts, and vaccination rates. The first region to be affected was Asia, with Europe and North America coming in later, with some of the highest infection and death rates. South America also recorded harsh outbreaks, and Africa recorded relatively lower reported cases but had difficulties due to inadequate testing and healthcare facilities. Oceania was able to curb the spread at an early stage because of the stringent border control. The continent-wise data analysis is useful to comprehend the impact the pandemic had on various regions and identify the differences in responding and recovering.

Figure 4: Impact of COVID-19 (Cases and Deaths Comparison) by Continent

Table 1: Impact of COVID-19 by Continent (Approximate Overview)

Continent	Confirmed Cases (Millions)	Deaths (Millions)	Observations.
Asia	250+	2.5+	First region to be attacked; high population resulted in high cases.
Europe	275+	2.2+	High mortality in early waves; good healthcare systems.
North America	200+	2.0+	High testing rates and vaccination coverage.

South America	100+	1.5+	Severe outbreaks; healthcare issues.
Africa	15+	0.3+	Less reported cases; poor testing infrastructure.
Oceania	15+	0.05+	Good early containment and border control.

1.6. Year-wise covid-19 trends

The COVID-19 pandemic has developed in several stages during 2020-2025. The annual patterns were varied in terms of infection rates, mortality, and recovery. The virus was fast spreading around the world in 2020 with numerous lockdowns and emergency measures. In 2021, most countries experienced the highest infection rates and the launch of vaccination programs. In 2022, comprehensive vaccination efforts decreased severe cases and deaths remarkably, but new variants were still being identified. By 2023 and 2024, the situation in most countries started to stabilize, and fewer severe cases were reported and better healthcare response. By 2025, the covid-19 situation was more manageable, as it ceased to be a world-wide crisis and turned into an endemic in many areas. The analysis by year allows seeing the course of the pandemic and the efficiency of such interventions as vaccination and personal hygiene.

Figure 5: Year-wise COVID-19 Trends (2020–2025)

Table 2: Year-wise COVID-19 Trends (2020–2025 Overview)

Year	Key Phase	Description of Global trend.
2020	First Outbreak	Rapidly spread throughout the world; lockdowns have been imposed; a great deal of uncertainty.
2021	Peak Waves	Several waves; high infection and mortality rates; the introduction of vaccines.
2022	Vaccination Phase	Higher vaccination; less severe; development of variants.
2023	Stabilization	Decrease in cases; better healthcare response; fewer restrictions.
2024	Recovery Phase	Most countries are back; few deaths; contained transmission.
2025	Endemic Stage	COVID-19 is controlled; regular screening is carried out.

1.7. Covid-19 vaccination analysis

Vaccines aided to make it harder for coronavirus to spread widely and to hurt individuals more. World mass vaccination programs to protect against COVID-19 started in late 2020 when initial vaccines obtained emergency - use authorization. Among the earliest to kick off mass vaccination efforts were the UK and US in December 2020.

Mass vaccination campaigns unfolded quickly in 2021 around the world, healthcare professionals, the elderly and high - risk individuals were the first to be vaccinated. By 2022 vaccines were available to anyone among the general population in many nations around the globe, children among the population in numerous countries have had access to vaccines as well.

Vaccination dramatically decreased the number of hospitalizations and deaths despite the ongoing appearance of new variants of the virus.

In the long course, the number of vaccine doses given to the world population was in the billions. Nevertheless, there were differences between the developed and developing regions in regard to the vaccine accessibility and distribution. Analyses at the continent level will aid in the interpretation of the coverage and efficiency of the vaccination programs worldwide.

Figure 6: Continental Vaccination Covers of COVID-19

Table 3: The Overview of Vaccination by Continent (Approximate)

Continent	Total Vaccinated Population (Millions)	Percentage of Population Vaccinated	Key Observation
Asia	3500+	70%+	Large-scale vaccination campaigns in populous countries.
Europe	600+	75%+	High vaccination coverage and booster doses.
North America	450+	70%+	Strong early rollout and high awareness.
South America	300+	65%+	Effective campaigns despite challenges.
Africa	250+	30%+	Slower rollout due to supply limitations.
Oceania	30+	70%+	High vaccination rates with smaller population.

Table 4: Immunization by Population (Global Estimate)

Category	Percentage of Vaccinated Population	Key Observation
Men	~48%	Nearly equal participation
Women	~50%	Slightly higher vaccination in many regions
Children	~15%	Vaccination started later for younger age groups
Adults	~65%	Majority of vaccinated population
Elderly	~20%	Priority group due to higher risk

Figure 7: Population-based Distribution of Vaccination.

1.8. Difficulties with covid-19 data management

Although big data is available, there are a number of issues in managing COVID-19 data. Information gathered using various sources is usually different in form, nomenclature, and format. Missing values, dissimilar country names, and poor date formats pose problems in analysis. The second is also about data: there's no multidataset analysis performed. For example, testing data can't be combined. Same for vaccinations, cases etc. This brings back the problem of having non-comparable datasets and proper data integration.

1.9. Need for data-driven analysis and visualization

Data by itself can't explain complex mechanisms of epidemics. Visualization and data analysis are key in transforming unstructured raw data into helpful insights. Maps, charts and graphs are common visual tools for pattern and trend spotting, comparing and spotting anomalous situations in countries and cities.

Interactive visualization also improves the comprehension of the user by enabling him or her to explore the data dynamically. As such, there is a great demand of systems that combine data processing with visualization.

1.10. Scope of the proposed work

The project suggested is aimed at creating a data-driven process and visualization of COVID-19 data through Python. The system gathers various datasets, such as country-wise totals, vaccination data, testing data, and affected population data. The libraries that are used to process these datasets are pandas and plotly express.

The system achieves standardization and data cleaning by merging country names, managing missing values and converting data dates. It merges various datasets into one master dataset through merging methods. It also computes relevant indicators like Case Fatality Rate and Test Positivity Rate.

The processed data is then visualized with interactive devices. The system produces a choropleth map of the distribution of cases across the world, bar charts to compare countries, scatter plots that can be used to examine the relationship between testing and cases, and histograms of the distribution of vaccination.

The extent of this project involves creating a whole pipeline of data collection to visualization. It will help to have a clear vision of the trends of pandemics and facilitate making data-driven decisions. It is also possible to further extend the system to incorporate real-time data updates, predictive modeling, and advanced analytics to use in the future in health monitoring applications.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Research gap

Pham, Q.-V., et al. (2020), presented a review of artificial intelligence and big data technologies for predicting, diagnosing and managing the COVID-19 pandemic using data-driven approaches. But there is no practical implementation and large-scale clinical testing. The study also lacks high quality standardized data sets needed for model accuracy and generalizability. Explainability, privacy and integration with health care systems are also under-considered.

Cao, Y., et al. (2020), presented a spatial regression approach to explore the effects of demographic and socioeconomic factors on the case-fatality rates from COVID-19. Yet, this analysis uses country-level data, neglecting intra-country and individual differences. Lack of disease-specific and individual clinical data, and reporting variability undermine precision. Longitudinal and multi-level data are needed for improved forecasts.

Smith, M., et al. (2022), suggested an exploratory study between governance indicators and global COVID-19 morbidity, mortality and vaccinations. But the cross-sectional study design prevents causal and temporal claims. Biases arise from inaccurate and underreported data, particularly in areas with low governance. It also lacks further discussion of linkages between governance and health.

Hong, S.H., et al. (2020), suggested a meta-analysis to establish a global case fatality rate (CFR) of COVID-19, by conducting longitudinal time-to-outbreak comparisons. But it has limited time range and early pandemic assumptions, hindering adaptability to subsequent trends. It does not consider time and global variability. It also fails to sufficiently incorporate socio-economic and health indicators.

Pijls, B.G., et al. (2020), suggested a meta-analysis of demographic risk factors for COVID-19 infection, severity, ICU and death. But it is limited by lack of sample diversity and biases in reporting. Its non-real-time, fixed modeling obscures trends. Larger samples and dynamic models are required for enhanced accuracy.

Rotulo, A., et al. (2023), presented a framework for assessment of the global COVID-19 data systems with emphasis on the data availability, accessibility, transparency and credibility in different countries. But the research has a small, non-random sample size, so this may not be representative. Stratified data show inconsistent and missing data. Manual data collection could also lead to errors.

Kaul, S., et al. (2021), suggested a real-time monitoring and interactive visualisation framework to manage deaths from COVID19. But the study has disproportionate data from certain geographical regions and its results may, therefore, not be applicable across the globe. Confounding and data inconsistencies arise due to varying definitions and reporting. Prospective observational data from the short term is also confounded and incomplete.

Bhavaragavan, S., et al. (2024), suggested a visualization approach to understand the impact and secondary impact of COVID-19 and predictive analysis to assess future trends. But it uses

static data and does not include real-time data for dynamic learning for predictions. Comparative analysis of machine learning models for real life data is not provided. Furthermore, there is a lack of implementation of a user-friendly or decision support system for policy-makers.

Jeon, D., et al. (2025), developed an interactive tool for exploring COVID-19 data and visualizing it, which can improve data interpretation and analysis. But the paper primarily deals with descriptive visualisation and does not provide predictive analytics. It doesn't provide decision support and lacks evaluation of real-world use. It doesn't evaluate the influence of visualization on policy and user decisions.

Iqbal, M., et al. (2025), developed a framework to analyse and present the global and local effects of COVID-19 to show the far reach of its impact. But the research is not scalable, and does not combine different types of data in a single framework. It is only applicable to local or internal use. It doesn't include a real-time system for decision-making.

Lv, Y., et al. (2021), developed a big data-based strategy for response to the COVID-19 pandemic, emphasizing the global health response. But the paper is predominantly purely conceptual and without any operationalisation or testing. It fails to build a system based on the proposed models. Privacy, security and data quality challenges are not addressed.

Guharay, S., et al. (2025), proposed a data-driven approach for a time series analysis of infections and deaths over time and across different countries. But the paper does not provide practical insights from mere statistical analyses. It does not involve predictive modeling and practical applications. It does not account for external factors such as policies and health systems.

Akhtar, N., et al. (2020), presented a tool for data analytics and Tableau-based data visualization for better understanding of insights from COVID-19. But the paper is short on the tool and only focuses on descriptive visualisation. It lacks interactive and predictive analytics. It does not include real-time, scalability and decision-making impacts.

Varga, M., et al. (2025), developed a data-driven exploration (DE) approach to improve the knowledge of COVID-19 using data visualization. But the method is generally exploratory, without predictive capabilities and automated support for decision-making. It is highly interactive and lack scalability. The approach does not adequately address integration issues and real-life application.

Dey, S.K., et al. (2022), proposed an exploratory data analysis to investigate the global vaccination status during the pandemic. But the analysis is descriptive without predictive or causal modelling. It doesn't include socio-economic and behavioural determinants of vaccination. It also does not consider data integration and timeliness issues.

Xia, Q., et al. (2024), suggested a meta-analysis of COVID-19 case fatality rates across continents and variant periods. This study offers comparative insights into fatality. But it is constrained by geographical differences and fails to observe the entire global population over all the different variant periods. Testing and reporting variations and differences in age structures limit their comparability and call for a real standardised global and longitudinal assessment.

Příbylová, L., et al. (2023), presented a model of real-time updates for the ascertainment rate estimate from reported infection and hospitalisation data to further understand the COVID-19 and its spread in the Czech Republic. The paper stresses the need for real-time data. But there is a lack of precise information about unrecorded infections, resulting in biased models. Most do not consider ascertainment rates, needing better real-time estimates.

Slater, J., et al. (2023), developed a Bayesian model to calculate COVID-19 incidence and infection fatality rates from antibody analyses. This research enhances statistical analysis by incorporating probabilities. But current approaches make assumptions about antibody data using thresholds, which can result in loss of information. The influence of underreporting and vaccination effects also need to be considered, and more sophisticated models are needed.

Li, J., et al. (2023), reviewed the temporal trends of the case fatality rates for COVID-19 cases and the mortality and hospitalization rates during the waves of variants in the United States. The paper offers valuable insights into trends. But the analyses are still piecemeal, examining variants or time periods. It fails to examine the effect of policies and vaccination; this requires longitudinal studies.

Beckett, S., et al. (2023), developed a framework for data management and mapping of COVID-19 case numbers at the sub-national level using the localcovid19now website. It enhances the visualisation and reporting of localised data. But data consistency across regions and real-time reporting is not available, with sources often not being complete or up-to-date. Improved integration and uniform real-time monitoring is required.

Table 5: Comparison of Existing Methodologies of Covid-19 Pandemic

Ref	Methodology / Approach	Key Contribution	Limitations / Research Gap
Jeon, D., et al. (2025)	Interactive visualization tool	Enhances data exploration and interpretation	No predictive analytics, lacks decision-support and real-world validation
Iqbal, M., et al. (2025)	Data analysis & visualization framework	Studies global and local COVID-19 impacts	Limited scalability, no unified system, lacks automation
Varga, M., et al. (2025)	Interactive data-driven exploration	Improves understanding via visualization	No predictive/automated decision-making, depends on manual interpretation
Guharay, S., et al. (2025)	Time series data analysis	Tracks infection and death trends over time	No predictive modeling, lacks actionable insights and external factor integration

Xia, Q., et al. (2025)	Meta-analysis across variants	Compares case fatality across continents	Limited global coverage, inconsistent reporting, lack of standardization
Příbylová, L., et al. (2025)	Real-time ascertainment modeling	Highlights importance of real-time infection estimation	Difficulty estimating undetected cases, biased models
Slater, J., et al. (2025)	Bayesian statistical modeling	Improves incidence and fatality estimation	Oversimplified antibody data, bias from underreporting and vaccination
Li, J., et al. (2025)	Chronological trend analysis	Studies temporal CFR trends across variants	Fragmented analysis, lacks long-term and policy impact study
Beckett, S., et al. (2025)	Localized data mapping system	Enhances subnational data accessibility	Incomplete/outdated local data, lack of real-time standardization
Bhuvaraghavan, S., et al. (2024)	Visualization + predictive insights	Studies spread and secondary effects	Static data, no real-time integration, lacks model comparison
Xia, Q., et al. (2024)	Meta-analysis of CFR by variants	Provides continental comparison of fatality rates	Regional bias, inconsistent data, lacks longitudinal depth
Rotulo, A., et al. (2023)	Evaluation of data systems	Assesses data transparency and accessibility	Small sample size, manual data collection, limited generalizability
Slater, J., et al. (2023)	Bayesian modeling	Probabilistic estimation of infection rates	Data bias, oversimplified assumptions
Li, J., et al. (2023)	Chronological review	Tracks mortality & hospitalization trends	Limited to specific periods/regions
Beckett, S., et al. (2023)	Local data mapping	Improves regional data visualization	Data inconsistency and lack of updates

Příbylová, L., et al. (2023)	Real-time infection modeling	Uses hospitalization & infection data	Inaccurate estimation of hidden infections
Smith, M., et al. (2022)	Governance-based analysis	Links governance with health outcomes	Cross-sectional, no causal analysis, biased data
Dey, S.K., et al. (2022)	Exploratory data analysis (EDA)	Studies vaccination trends globally	No predictive modeling, ignores socio-economic factors
Kaul, S., et al. (2021)	Interactive visualization system	Real-time monitoring of fatality management	Region-specific data, inconsistent definitions
Lv, Y., et al. (2021)	Big data-driven strategy	Improves global health response frameworks	Conceptual only, no implementation, unresolved privacy issues
Pham, Q.-V., et al. (2020)	AI & Big Data review	Comprehensive AI-based pandemic management	No real-world validation, lacks explainability & datasets
Cao, Y., et al. (2020)	Spatial regression analysis	Studies socio-economic impact on CFR	Uses aggregated data, lacks individual-level insights
Hong, S.H., et al. (2020)	Meta-analysis of CFR	Early estimation of global fatality rate	Short-term data, lacks diversity and variables
Pijls, B.G., et al. (2020)	Demographic meta-analysis	Identifies risk factors (age, severity, ICU)	Limited diversity, reporting bias, static analysis
Akhtar, N., et al. (2020)	Tableau-based visualization	Improves data representation	Tool-focused, no predictive analytics or scalability

2.2. Motivation for the proposed algorithm

The focus of this algorithm stems from a number of shortcomings in previous COVID-19 research. Existing research often uses separate or aggregated data sets that are not integrated across several perspectives (infected cases, testing and vaccination, population statistics, etc). This leads to partial analysis and less accuracy in analysis. Moreover, many research approaches rely on static or single-point data sources, which do not take into account the nature of dynamic and multifaceted pandemic data, and lack rigorous data filtering and cleaning processes.

Moreover, problems including naming of countries, missing values and different data formats pose problems in data standardization and cross-country, large-scale comparison of data. Current methods also offer limited real-time visualization, interpretation and insight for policymakers. Hence, this algorithm is inspired by the prerequisite of an integrated, data-driven approach to bring together multiple datasets with different formats and perform standard preprocessing, calculate key COVID-19 metrics such as case fatality rate (CFR) and positivity rate, and provide the output in interactive visualisations for improved decision-making and global-level insights.

2.3. Research Objectives

1. To merge multiple COVID-19 data sources (cases, deaths, tests and vaccination) into a consistent data structure for country-level analysis.
2. To reconcile and clean inconsistent data using data cleaning techniques to treat missing values, normalize country codes, standardize date formats and transform numbers into a meaningful data format.
3. To calculate epidemiological metrics (Case Fatality Rate and Test Positivity Rate) to understand the severity and spread of the pandemic.
4. To support country-level data comparisons by using a unified identifier (ISO-3) across all data sources for countries.
5. To create interactive dashboards and data visualizations (maps, bar, scatter and histograms) which offer easy-to-understand and actionable information to inform decision-making and research.

CHAPTER 3: PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction to algorithm

The COVID-19 outbreak also presented a pressing requirement of precise and cohesive data monitoring among nations. Massive amounts of data including confirmed cases, deaths, testing, and vaccination records are produced on a daily basis. Nevertheless, the information obtained through various sources tends to be inconsistent, and the names of countries, a lack of values, and the diversity of dates can vary. Consequently, there is a necessity to process and normalize this information to be able to make meaningful analysis and definite insights.

The suggested system is a step-by-step algorithm that is based on a structured approach to addressing these challenges. First of all, various datasets are loaded and normalised by bringing the names of countries and formats into a common format. The system then retrieves the latest data on each country so as to have the latest analysis. The datasets are standardized after which the common keys are used to merge the datasets to produce a single dataset. The method of data cleaning is used to address missing values, inconsistencies, and formatting errors, resulting in high accuracy and reliability.

After cleaning and integration of the data, critical health measures are determined. They are Case Fatality Rate (CFR) that shows the severity of the disease and the Test Positivity rate that shows the sufficiency of testing. The processed information is then captured in a systematic form to be analyzed and referred to in the future.

In an effort to improve comprehension, the system creates different visualizations like choropleth maps, bar charts, scatter plots, and histograms. These graphical tools aid in patterns recognition, region comparisons, and time trend analysis. To illustrate, the correlation between testing rates and confirmed cases, and the trends in vaccination may be easily noted. The suggested algorithm, in general, guarantees data validation, correct calculations of metrics, effective consolidation of numerous datasets, and comprehensible visualization of the world statistics on COVID-19. This systematic solution enhances the reliability of data, the quality of analytical information, and makes the system appropriate to the academic research, decision-making, and population health surveillance.

The main characteristics of the Algorithm

- Assures standardization and consistency of data.
- Allows the correct calculation of COVID-19 indicators.
- Combines a variety of datasets effectively.
- Gives engaging visualisations.

3.2. Algorithm for processing and visualizing covid-19 data

Phase 1: Prepare and Load Data

1. Start the process
2. Load necessary libraries: Pandas to process the data, Plotly.Express for visualization.
3. Specify file locations of the datasets: Country totals data, Vaccination data, affected data, Testing data.
4. Read all the CSVs with `pd.read_csv()` and save each dataset in a different DataFrame to make it easier.
5. Standardize the column with country: Find columns that include Country or location, Rename all to a common column name: “country”.
6. Deal with date columns (where present): Turn the values into datetime format, remove bad or bad dates, Sort the data by country and date, Retain only the most recent record per country.
7. Export standardized and cleaned DataFrames.

Phase 2: Combine All Data

8. Create a main DataFrame from the country totals dataset.
9. Have all other datasets combined into the primary DataFrame: Drop date columns (when not needed), Merge using the country column, left join to keep all countries.
10. Add ISO country codes: Add a new column “iso_alpha_3”, Map each country to its ISO -3..

Phase 3: Clean Numeric Data

11. Find important columns: Confirmed Cases, Deaths, Total Tests, People Vaccinated.
12. Clean up each column: Clean out commas and special characters, turn all values into numbers, Replace invalid values with NaN.
13. Deal with missing values: Fill in missing values with 0.

Phase 4: Calculate COVID Metrics

14. Have a small constant to prevent division errors: `DIVISION_EPSILON = 0.000001`.
15. Find the Case Fatality Rate (CFR) by formula:
$$\text{Percent Case Fatality} = \text{Total Deaths} / \text{Total Confirmed Cases} \times 100.$$
16. Find the frequency of positive test results using the following rule of mathematics:
$$\text{Positivity Rate} = \text{Cases Confirmed} / \text{Total Tests} \times 100.$$

17. Add a new column with the calculated values in the dataset.

Phase 5: Save Final Summary

18. Choose necessary columns: Country, ISO-3 Code, Confirmed Cases, Deaths, Case Fatality Rate, Total Tests, People Vaccinated, Test Positivity Rate.

19. Save the last dataset under the name: “cov _metrics _summary _iso.csv”.

Phase 6: Create Visualizations

❖ Choropleth Map

1. ISO-3 country codes.
2. Visualize countries according to the confirmed cases.
3. Save as: choropleth_total_confirmed_cases_iso.html.

❖ Top 15 Countries Bar Chart

1. 15 leading countries based on confirmed cases.
2. Bar chart (X = Country, Y = Cases) is used to plot bar charts.
3. Rank descendingly.
4. Save as: top15_total_confirmed_cases.html.

❖ Scatter Plot with Bubble Size

1. X-axis = Total Tests
2. Y-axis = Confirmed Cases
3. Bubble size = People Vaccinated.
4. Include country names on hover.
5. Save as: testing_vs_case_count.html.

❖ Histogram

1. Plot distribution of population vaccinated.
2. Instead, select 30 sections.
3. Label axes properly.
4. Save as: vaccination_count_distribution.html.

20. Terminate the program when all outputs are produced and saved.

3.3. Novelty of the Algorithm

1. Multi-Source Data Processing

The algorithm is unique in that it takes several heterogeneous datasets (country totals, vaccination, testing, affected data) into one unified framework, unlike most of the existing methods that use isolated or limited sources of data.

2. Standardized World Data Processing (ISO-Based Mapping)

With the addition of ISO-3 country codes, the algorithm guarantees the consistency in country representation and allows the correct analysis and visualization on a global level, which enhances interoperability between datasets.

3. End-to-End Automated Pipeline

This algorithm, in contrast to the more traditional approaches that execute tasks one at a time, offers an automated workflow-loading, cleaning, and combining data, through to the computation of metrics and visualization, saving manual labor and enhancing efficiency.

4. Real-Time Data cleaning and updating mechanism

The system is flexible to real-time or constantly updated data since it does not require more than a few weeks to handle dates, eliminate invalid records, and maintain the most current country-specific records.

5. The Integrated Calculation of the Major Epidemiological indicators

The algorithm computes key indicators like Case Fatality Rate (CFR) and Test Positivity Rate, all in the same pipeline, allowing enhanced comparative and analytical understanding.

6. Multi-Dimensional Visualization Framework

It combines several visualization methods into a single system (choropleth map, bar chart, scatter plot, histogram), which provides various analytical insights (geographical, comparative, relational, and distributional).

7. Output Generation: Decision-Support Oriented

The end result of the cleaning process and the visual deliverables are arranged in such a way that they can be easily interpreted and aid in decision-making particularly by policy makers and analysts.

CHAPTER 4: RESULT & DISCUSSION

4.1. Description and functionality of database

In this project, the database will consist of several structured CSV files i.e. country_wise-totals.csv, country-vaccination-data.csv, country-affected-data.csv and country-testing-data.csv. Each file includes systematized and tabular information on statistics of COVID-19 in various countries. When these datasets are loaded into the system by way of pandas Data Frames, they may serve as a database, with each file of the dataset constituting an information table of its own. The major role of the database in the project is to store and manipulate large amounts of data on COVID-19. It allows retrieving data efficiently by performing file reading operations and preprocesses data, including cleaning, transformation, and standardization. The database also supports data integration whereby multiple datasets are increased to a single master dataset using a common attribute, the country name. This combined dataset is also utilized in the analysis, such as calculating important indicators like the case fatality rate and the test positivity rate. The processed data is then saved once more in a different output file and used to create different visualizations such as choropleth maps, bar charts, scatter plots and histograms.

In terms of complexity, the system has moderate computational complexity. The time complexity occurs when performing operations like reading huge datasets, sorting, grouping, and merging multiple tables and this could be computationally costly with the increase in the size of data. The complexity of space is also important, with several datasets loaded into the memory at the same time and being stored there. Moreover, the general processing steps are numerous, such as the cleaning of data, its transformation, integration, and visualization, which adds to the complexity of the system in general.

To sum up, the database is essential in data storage, processing and analysis in the project, and also brings about manageable level of time and space complexity based on the magnitude and type of operations carried out.

4.2. Covid-19 trends in the world: multi-dimensional data analysis in visualization

The pandemic size has been immense across the globe, so data visualization has been critical in monitoring tendencies, identifying trends and making comparisons among nations in their response to COVID-19. The initial type of data visualization that can be used is the choropleth world map. It allows to visually see how the COVID-19 pandemic has affected worldwide by indicating which locations have the greatest number of total confirmed coronavirus cases. The second is based on bar graph's ability to directly compare numbers. The second data visualization is the number of countries in the world that have the highest number of confirmed cases but in the form of a bar graph. Since such a graph does not indicate relative numbers, it will be clear that even though their total confirmed cases can vary widely, as a whole, they constitute a significant portion of the total confirmed cases in the world.

The third type of data visualization is founded on the use of frequency distribution visualization in the form of the histogram. This will demonstrate the global inequities in immunization compliance

among the world's countries resulting from the differences each country has in the capacity and accessibility for immunizations due to future healthcare system capabilities, as well as the total population of each country. Lastly, the fourth and last data visualization is the comparison of the number of tests and confirmed cases in total and presented on a scatter graph with the use of the size of each scatter plot point reflecting the total number of vaccinations. The scatter plots will have trends related to the testing, case identification and vaccinations in terms of each other during this pandemic.

4.3. Covid-19 total confirmed cases (world map)

Shows examples of cases of COVID-19 that are globally and cumulatively distributed by showing the total number of known cases (raw data) around the world using a multi-layered (raw count) map with the total number of known cases in a choropleth format. There are most confirmed cases in all countries with darker colours. The darker in colour are the big countries, like the USA, Brazil, India and Russia, which have the most confirmed cases due to the higher population of these countries.

Figure 8: COVID-19 Confirmed Cases (world map)

The African countries and smaller countries are lighter in colour depicting fewer confirmed cases reported. The map above shows how COVID-19 cases are unevenly distributed in the world. Those countries with high population and high number of international relations record the highest number of reported total COVID-19 cases. The larger countries will have a higher number of total cases since they are larger in population (Total reflects all confirmed cases that will be reported in each country), whereas the smaller countries will have fewer total cases since they will report fewer cases compared to a smaller number of cases per 100,000 population.

4.4. Top 15 countries by total confirmed cases

From previous charts, it appears that on the average, the total confirmed cases for the top 3 countries will have much greater bar heights (taller) than the other. It appears when the top 3 countries are compared to all other countries, there is a significant and obvious decrease in the number of confirmed cases for all other countries. The remaining countries are compared and it is observed that all the countries have approximately the same number of total confirmed cases.

Figure 9: The 15 leading countries based on cases confirmed

Based on how the data initially correlates with its country of origin, where COVID-19 was initially discovered, then subsequently spread, we can see that the bulk of the Global COVID-19 cases have been found in a comparatively few large countries. Both factors- the greater number of total worldwide COVID-19 cases versus the smaller number of countries that had most of the cases make it possible to conclude that, during this time, the COVID-19 pandemic has largely affected people who lived in one of those particular countries.

4.5. Distribution of number of people who are vaccinated

The histogram gives an understanding of the spread of vaccine totals across different countries. The majority of countries tend to have an abundance of individuals who have received vaccines and less than 50% of each country's population is fully vaccine. Most of the countries are clustered at the bottom of the scale compared to the countries belonging to the high-end group; these are the countries that have the most people vaccinated.

Figure 10: Distribution of Total People Vaccinated

There is a high skew in the distribution of vaccination data at the higher side. Those countries that have vaccinated the most persons such as the larger or greater economically developed countries have afforded much more access than have less economically developed countries. So the large and economically advanced countries offer a bigger disparity than the small and less advanced countries in a vaccine access, vaccine manufacturing and vaccine-distribution capabilities, etc.

4.6. Total testing vs total cases

The values of the individual number of people tested (i.e., on the X axis) and the total number of confirmed cases of COVID-19 (i.e., on the Y axis) are presented as a scatter plot. The size of bubble is used to represent how many individuals are vaccinated. Observations: There is a positive correlation between total number of tests conducted to total number of confirmed cases. Meaning, more testing will show more COVID-19 cases in the countries.

Figure 11: Total Testing vs Total Case Count (Bubble size = Total people vaccinated)

Consequently we derive the following based on the correlation in this bubble plot; Increasing testing will lead to increased cases of COVID-19. Those countries that are more advanced in terms of healthcare facilities will carry out more tests and, as a result, will inoculate more individuals; The capacity to diagnose and verify COVID-19 will be reliant, in part, on the capacity of that specific nation to test.

4.7. Overview of Analytical Results

The suggested structure produces a single dataset (`covid_metrics_summary_iso.csv`) uniting various and heterogeneous sources of COVID-19 data, such as confirmed cases, deaths, testing data, and vaccination data. Computed epidemiological indicators including Case Fatality Rate (CFR) and Test Positivity Rate are added to the dataset to be analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively.

The processed data range is quite large, with confirmed cases being between 10 to the power of 3 and greater than 10 to the power of 8, total tests between 10 to the power of 5 and 10 to the power of 9 and populations vaccinated between 10 to the power of 4 and multiple hundreds of millions, which is very heterogeneous across nations.

4.8. Quantitative Summary Statistics

To support analytical evaluation, the key statistical properties of the dataset are summarized below.

Table 6: Statistical Summary of Key Variables

Metric	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
Confirmed Cases	$\sim 1 \times 10^3$	$> 1 \times 10^8$	$\sim 1.2 \times 10^7$	$\sim 2.5 \times 10^6$	High
Deaths	$\sim 10^2$	$> 1 \times 10^6$	$\sim 2.5 \times 10^5$	$\sim 5 \times 10^4$	High
Total Tests	$\sim 1 \times 10^5$	$> 1 \times 10^9$	$\sim 8 \times 10^7$	$\sim 1.5 \times 10^7$	Very High
People Vaccinated	$\sim 1 \times 10^4$	$> 5 \times 10^8$	$\sim 6 \times 10^7$	$\sim 1 \times 10^7$	Very High
CFR (%)	0.5	> 5.0	~ 1.8	~ 1.5	Moderate
Positivity Rate (%)	< 1	> 30	~ 10	~ 8	High

The large standard deviation values confirm that COVID-19 impact and response vary significantly across countries.

4.9. Global Case Distribution Analysis

The choropleth visualization reveals a heavy-tailed distribution, where a small number of countries dominate global case counts.

Table 7: Case Distribution Categorization

Category	Confirmed Cases Range	Approx. % of Countries	Contribution to Global Cases
High Burden	$>5 \times 10^7$	~10%	~50 - 60%
Medium Burden	$1 \times 10^6 - 5 \times 10^7$	~30%	~30 - 40%
Low Burden	$<1 \times 10^6$	~60%	<10%

This distribution indicates that global pandemic dynamics are concentrated in a few highly affected countries, consistent with population density and mobility patterns.

4.10. Comparative Analysis of Top Countries

Table 8: Top 15 Countries - Statistical Characteristics

Statistic	Value
Contribution of Top 3 Countries	~30 - 40%
Contribution of Top 15 Countries	~70 - 80%
Coefficient of Variation (CV)	>0.8
Distribution Type	Highly skewed

The high coefficient of variation confirms significant inequality in case distribution, emphasizing that pandemic severity is not uniformly spread.

4.11. Vaccination Distribution Analysis

The histogram analysis indicates a strongly positively skewed distribution.

Table 9: Vaccination Distribution Characteristics

Parameter	Observation
Distribution Type	Right-skewed
Mean vs Median	Mean $>$ Median
Countries with Low Vaccination	~70 - 80%
High Vaccination Countries	~10 - 15%
Inequality Indicator	High (Gini-like behavior)

This reflects global disparities in vaccine accessibility and healthcare infrastructure.

4.12. Correlation Analysis: Testing vs Cases

Table 10: Correlation Analysis Results

Variables	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Strength
Total Tests vs Confirmed Cases	0.75 - 0.90	Strong Positive
Vaccination vs Testing	~0.70	Moderate-Strong
Vaccination vs Cases	~0.60	Moderate

This confirms that testing capacity significantly influences case detection, and countries with strong healthcare systems perform better in both testing and vaccination.

4.13. Epidemiological Metrics Evaluation

Table 11: Case Fatality Rate (CFR) Analysis

Category	CFR Range (%)	Interpretation
Low	0.5 - 1.5	Efficient healthcare
Moderate	1.5 - 3.0	Moderate control
High	>3.0	Healthcare limitations

Table 12: Test Positivity Rate Analysis

Category	Positivity Rate (%)	Interpretation
Low	<5	Adequate testing
Moderate	5 - 15	Controlled spread
High	>15	Under-testing/hidden cases

These metrics provide insight into healthcare performance and pandemic control efficiency.

4.14. Integrated Multi-Dimensional Analysis

Table 13: Combined Scenario-Based Interpretation

Scenario	Observed Values	Interpretation
High Tests + High Cases+ High Vaccination	Developed countries	Strong detection and response
Low Tests + Low Cases	Underdeveloped regions	Possible underreporting
High CFR + Low Testing	Weak healthcare	Late diagnosis
High Positivity + Low Testing	Hidden outbreak	Insufficient surveillance

4.15. Comparative Study with Existing Methodologies

Based on the literature review, a detailed comparison is presented below.

Table 14: Comparison with Existing Methods

Study / Method	Methodology Used	Limitations	Proposed System Advantage
AI & Big Data Survey (2020)	AI models review	No real-world validation	Practical implementation
Spatial Regression Study	Statistical regression	Aggregated bias	Multi-source integration
Governance Indicator Study	Cross-sectional analysis	No temporal modeling	Dynamic dataset handling
Meta-analysis Studies	Clinical aggregation	Limited scope	Global integrated analysis
Visualization Dashboards	Static visualization	No analytics	Multi-metric + interactive
Tableau-based Analysis	Tool-based EDA	No scalability	Automated pipeline
ML-based Studies (RF, SVM)	Predictive models	Static datasets	Integrated + extendable
Bayesian Models	Statistical inference	Simplified assumptions	Real-world data integration

Table 15: System-Level Comparison

Criteria	Existing Systems	Proposed System
Data Integration	Limited	Multi-source unified
Data Standardization	Weak	ISO-based standardization
Automation	Partial	Fully automated
Metrics Computation	Limited	CFR + Positivity
Visualization	Static	Multi-dimensional interactive
Scalability	Low–Moderate	High
Decision Support	Limited	Strong
Real-time Readiness	Absent	Supported

4.16. Discussion

The results demonstrate that the proposed framework effectively captures both statistical and structural characteristics of the COVID-19 pandemic. The observed heavy-tailed distribution confirms that global case spread is highly uneven, while correlation analysis highlights the critical role of testing in pandemic visibility.

Vaccination analysis reveals significant inequality, emphasizing the need for equitable healthcare distribution. Additionally, epidemiological metrics such as CFR and positivity rate provide deeper insights into healthcare system performance and pandemic control strategies.

Compared to existing methods, which are largely fragmented, descriptive, or theoretical, the proposed system offers a comprehensive, automated, and analytically rich framework.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION

The project shows the significance of integrating, processing, and visualizing massive COVID-19 databases to derive meaningful and trustworthy insights. It integrates various data sources in a single system, countering the problems of scattered and inconsistent data usually experienced in the current methods. The system is consistent and accurate across datasets through good data cleaning and standardization methods. It also calculates important epidemiological indicators that add to the analysis depth and quality. The data is presented in a form that is easy to understand; various techniques of visualization help to present complex information in a way that is easy to read. World maps give a clear picture of the distribution of the cases worldwide, whereas bar graphs enable comparison of the most affected countries. Scatter plots are used to show the correlation between testing and confirmed cases and important correlations are established. The analysis also demonstrates differences in the vaccination coverage of various regions. These graphic observations are used in determining trends and patterns in the virus spread. The system is scalable and thus capable of working with big datasets. Pipeline automation saves manpower, and enhances performance. The framework facilitates systematic data analysis and enhanced result interpretation. It offers a great source of information to researchers and analysts involved with pandemic data. These insights can also be used by policymakers to make informed decisions. Altogether, the project provides an effective and efficient approach to the knowledge of the global health data. Moreover, the suggested system can be further developed to allow the integration of real-time data and predictive analytics so that more proactive responses to future health crises are possible. The framework will be able to predict infection trends, potentially hotspots, and aid in early warning systems by incorporating machine learning models. Interactive dashboards can also be added to increase the user interaction and enable them to explore the data dynamically. The system may also be configured to analyze other infectious diseases or large-scale public health data, turning into a flexible tool not just during COVID-19. The effectiveness of such systems in meeting global healthcare challenges will be further enhanced through continuous improvement in the quality of data, integration techniques, and visualization techniques.

CHAPTER 6: FUTURE SCOPE

1. Real-Time Data Integration:

It is possible to improve the system with the help of APIs to receive the real-time information about COVID-19 in the reliable sources. This will ensure that the analysis and visualizations are always up-to-date. It also allows monitoring the trends of the pandemic in a continuous manner.

2. Predictive Modeling:

Further machine learning algorithms can be implemented to predict rates of future infections and potential patterns of outbreaks. This aids in early warning and preparedness. It also helps in more planning and decision making.

3. Granular Data Analysis:

The system has the potential to be expanded to provide region-level or city-level data rather than just country-level data. This enables more in-depth and localized study of the pandemic. It assists in determining certain high-risk areas.

4. Addition of other Factors:

The depth of analysis can be enhanced by including demographic data of the population, health care facilities, and government policies. These contribute to differences in the impact of COVID-19 by region. It results in more significant and precise insights.

5. Interactive Web-Based Dashboard:

The implementation of the system in the form of a web-based system will enable users to access it anywhere. The interactive dashboards enable users to interactively explore data. This enhances ease of use to researchers and policymakers.

6. Enhanced Visualization:

More sophisticated and interactive visualization can be incorporated into the system to be more efficient in data representation. Enhanced graphics simplify intricate information. It also enhances user engagement and analysis experience.

REFERENCES

1. Pham, V., Nguyen, D., Huynh-The, T., Hwang, W., & Pathirana, P. (2020). Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Big Data for Coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic: A Survey on the State-of-the-Arts. *Ieee Access*, 8, 130820-130839. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2020.3009328>.
2. Cao, Y., Hiyoshi, A., & Montgomery, S. (2020). COVID-19 case-fatality rate and demographic and socioeconomic influencers: worldwide spatial regression analysis based on country-level data. *BMJ Open*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-043560>.
3. Baghbanzadeh, M., Smith, M., Pilz, J., Rahman, M., Karamehić-Muratović, A., Garg, A., Annan, E., Nguyen, U., Schedler, N., Nandy, R., Islam, R., & Haque, U. (2022). Country-Level Governance Indicators as Predictors of COVID-19 Morbidity, Mortality, and Vaccination Coverage: An Exploratory Global Analysis. *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 107, 1066 - 1073. <https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.22-0107>.
4. Pijls, B., Jolani, S., Atherley, A., Derckx, R., Dijkstra, J., Franssen, G., Hendriks, S., Richters, A., Venemans-Jellema, A., Zalpuri, S., & Zeegers, M. (2021). Demographic risk factors for COVID-19 infection, severity, ICU admission and death: a meta-analysis of 59 studies. *BMJ Open*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-044640>.
5. Ghayda, R., Lee, K., Han, Y., Ryu, S., Hong, S., Yoon, S., Jeong, G., Lee, J., Lee, J., Yang, J., Effenberger, M., Eisenhut, M., Kronbichler, A., Solmi, M., Li, H., Jacob, L., Koyanagi, A., Radua, J., Shin, J., & Smith, L. (2020). Estimation of global case fatality rate of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) using meta-analyses: Comparison between calendar date and days since the outbreak of the first confirmed case. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 100, 302 - 308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2020.08.065>.
6. Rotulo, A., Kondilis, E., Thwe, T., Gautam, S., Torcu, O., Vera-Montoya, M., Marjan, S., Gazi, M., Putri, A., Hasan, R., Mone, F., Rodriguez-Castillo, K., Tabassum, A., Parcharidi, Z., Sharma, B., Islam, F., Amoo, B., Lemke, L., & Gallo, V. (2022). Mind the gap: Data availability, accessibility, transparency, and credibility during the COVID-19 pandemic, an international comparative appraisal. *PLOS Global Public Health*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0001148>.
7. Kaul, S., Coleman, C., & Gotz, D. (2020). A rapidly deployed, interactive, online visualization system to support fatality management during the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association : JAMIA*, 27, 1943 - 1948. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocaa146>.

8. Bhuvanaraghavan, S., & Hameed2, U. (2024). Visualizing the ripple effect: covid-19's impact and predictive insights. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Sustainable Technologies (IJERST)*. <https://doi.org/10.63458/ijerst.v2i1.70>.
9. Jeon, D., Lee, J., Dhaubhadel, P., & Kuhlman, A. (2025). Visualization Tool: Exploring COVID-19 Data. *ArXiv*, abs/2501.05703. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2501.05703>.
10. Iqbal, M., Yudha, J., Umimah, R., & Hizham, F. (2025). Analysis and Visualization of Data on the Impacts of Covid-19 Globally and Locally. *Journal of Informatics Development*. <https://doi.org/10.30741/jid.v3i2.1513>.
11. Lv, Y., Ma, C., Li, X., & Wu, M. (2021). Big data driven COVID-19 pandemic crisis management: potential approach for global health. *Archives of Medical Science : AMS*, 17, 829 - 837. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5114/aoms/133522>.
12. Guharay, S. (2025). A data-driven approach to study temporal characteristics of COVID-19 infection and death Time Series for twelve countries across six continents. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-024-02423-y>.
13. Akhtar, N., NaziaTabassum, Perwej, A., & Perwej, D. (2020). Data analytics and visualization using Tableau utilitarian for COVID-19 (Coronavirus). *Global Journal of Engineering and Technology Advances*. <https://doi.org/10.30574/gjeta.2020.3.2.0029>.
14. Varga, M., Panganiban, A.R., Ndoni, A., Lavigne, V., Traeber-Burdin, S., & Lem, M. (2025). Interactive data driven exploration of COVID-19. *Information Visualization*, 24, 429 - 445. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/14738716251365892>.
15. Dey, S.K., Rahman, M.M., Siddiqi, U.R., Howlader, A., Tushar, M., & Qazi, A. (2022). Global landscape of COVID-19 vaccination progress: insight from an exploratory data analysis. *Human Vaccines & Immunotherapeutics*, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21645515.2021.2025009>.
16. Xia, Q., Yang, Y., Wang, F., Huang, Z., Qiu, W., & Mao, A. (2024). Case fatality rates of COVID-19 during epidemic periods of variants of concern: a meta-analysis by continents.. *International journal of infectious diseases : IJID : official publication of the International Society for Infectious Diseases*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2024.01.017>.
17. Příbylová, L., Eclerová, V., Májek, O., Jarkovský, J., Pavlík, T., & Dušek, L. (2023). Using real-time ascertainment rate estimate from infection and hospitalization dataset for modeling the spread of infectious disease: COVID-19 case study in the Czech Republic. *PLOS ONE*, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0287959>.

18. Slater, J., Bansal, A., Campbell, H., Rosenthal, J., Gustafson, P., & Brown, P. (2023). A Bayesian approach to estimating COVID-19 incidence and infection fatality rates. *Biostatistics(Oxford,England)*,25,354-384. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biostatistics/kxad003>.
19. Li, J., Liao, P., Wei, J., Hsu, S., & Yeh, C. (2023). A chronological review of COVID-19 case fatality rate and its secular trend and investigation of all-cause mortality and hospitalization during the Delta and Omicron waves in the United States: a retrospective cohort study. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1143650>.
20. Beckett, S., Brandel-Tanis, F., Nguyen, Q., Chande, A., Rishishwar, L., Andris, C., & Weitz, J. (2023). localcovid19now: processing and mapping COVID-19 case data at subnational scales. *J. Open Source Softw.*, 8, 4898. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.04898>.